

Unlocking the Potential of Human-Robot Synergy under Advanced Industrial Applications: The FEROX Simulator*

Beril Yalcinkaya^{1,2}[0000-0001-8411-722X], André Araújo¹[0000-0003-1507-4945],
Micael Couceiro¹[0000-0001-6641-6090], Salviano Soares²[0000-0001-5862-5706],
and António Valente²[0000-0002-5798-1298]

¹ Ingeniarius, Ltd., R. Nossa Sra. Conceição 146, Alfena, 4445-147, Portugal

² School of Sciences and Technology-Engineering Department, University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro (UTAD), Quinta de Prados, Vila Real, 5000-801, Portugal
beril, andre, micael@ingeniarius.pt salblues, avalente@utad.pt

Abstract. Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) in advanced industrial scenarios has emerged as a transformative force. Modern robots, infused with artificial intelligence (AI), can enhance human capabilities, offering a wide spectrum of opportunities in agriculture, forestry, construction and many other domains. However, the complex nature of HRC demands realistic simulators to bridge the gap between theory and practice. This paper introduces the FEROX Simulator, purpose-built for robot-assisted wild berry collection. We briefly delve into the simulator’s capabilities to showcase its potential as a platform to develop HRC systems. Our research underscores the need for simulators designed for challenging HRC contexts and aims to inspire further advancements in this domain.

Keywords: human-robot collaboration · robotic simulators · advanced industrial applications.

1 Introduction

Robots have transcended the realm of science fiction to become indispensable in our daily lives, assisting us in tasks ranging from the mundane to the complex. Yet, their true potential lies not in isolation, but in collaboration with humans [1]. This is the essence of Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) - a burgeoning field where humans and robots join forces to achieve feats beyond their individual capabilities. In an era marked by artificial intelligence (AI) and modern robotics, imbuing robots with intelligent algorithms for HRC has become a pivotal research focus. The fusion of human prowess with robotic precision and endurance opens doors to a spectrum of tasks performed more efficiently.

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1.1 Research question and objective

Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) holds immense promise across various sectors, including agriculture, forestry, and construction. However, designing effective HRC systems is challenging. Robots must not only excel at tasks but also understand and respond to human behaviour, which is dynamic and unpredictable. To address these complexities, researchers turn to advanced virtual environments like simulators and digital twins. These tools provide controlled spaces for developing, testing, and optimizing robotic systems, all while exploring human-robot interactions without the need for physical equipment [10].

However, the current shortage of simulators for Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) is a significant challenge. Existing frameworks such as Gazebo [4], MORSE [3], USARSim [2], CoppeliaSim [9], ARGoS [7], RoboNetSim [5], primarily focus on robot-only applications, leaving a gap in simulating modern collaborative robots. This paper introduces the FEROX Simulator, tailored for robot-assisted wild berry collection, offering a comprehensive virtual environment for effective HRC. Our research aims to inspire further innovation in the pivotal domain of HRC by offering a realistic platform to test and optimise systems under such challenging applications..

2 The FEROX Simulator

FEROX, a Horizon Framework Programme initiative funded by the EU, harmoniously integrates human elements with cutting-edge robotic technologies, aiming to revolutionise the wild berry industry ³. This innovative approach reimagines berry picking, mitigating the physical and mental strains on pickers, while enhancing safety and efficiency in HRC.

2.1 General architecture

The FEROX simulator accommodates interactions involving both single and multiple humans and robots, supporting various short and long-term HRC scenarios. The FEROX Simulator comprises two distinct types of instances: (i) **Human Instance**, which may comprehend multiple instances, each enabling the control of a single virtual human agents; and (ii) **Robot Instance**, which is a single instance running on a server machine, put together to manage robotic agents and other mission- and environmental-related conditions as shown in Fig. 1 .

The multiple human instances coexisting within the same network seamlessly communicate with the robot instance via the Robot Operating System (ROS), utilising topics for data exchange and action servers to initiate specific robotic tasks [8]. The simulator’s architecture forms a robust foundation for its diverse range of features, which we will delve into in subsequent sections.

³ <https://ferox.fbk.eu/>

Fig. 1. The general overview of the Ferox Simulator.

2.2 Ecosystem

In the FEROX Simulator, two pivotal components come together to create a versatile platform for simulating complex HRC scenarios: Unity and ROS. Unity, as a leading game engine, provides the foundation for creating a realistic and immersive simulation environment, including a powerful physics engine and sophisticated rendering capabilities. ROS, on the other hand, serves as the backbone of the FEROX Simulator [6]. Its adoption also ensures that the simulator can seamlessly transition into the real world, as it operates within the same ROS ecosystem used by robots. This means that the robot instance can be readily replaced with real robots, facilitating a smooth transition from simulation to practical deployment.

The ROS TCP Connector ⁴ plays a crucial role in seamless integration, serving as the linchpin connecting human and robot instances. It orchestrates synchronization through ROS topics and ROS services, facilitating the coordination of human operator movements from the Human Instance to the robot instance. It also triggers ROS services in the Robot Instance, replicating them in the Human Instance, ensuring fidelity and accuracy in the FEROX Simulator.

2.3 Environments

In the FEROX Simulator, Unity engine capabilities enable easy customization of immersive scenarios for advanced applications without extensive programming skills. Currently, scenario replication is needed for both robot and human instances. Future developments aim to simplify this process by enabling content

⁴ <https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/ROS-TCP-Connector>

transfer from the robot instance to the human instance, similar to multiplayer online games.

Interactable objects, like berries in robot-assisted picking, are managed by the robot instance within virtual environments. For example, the robot instance generates random berry locations and broadcasts them to connected human instances. Human-initiated actions, such as berry picking, occur in the human instance and are transmitted to the robot instance, updating berry states across all human instances. This bidirectional communication ensures a dynamic and realistic HRC environment with immediate and coherent consequences for both human and robot actions.

2.4 Robots

FEROX Simulator seamlessly integrates with ROS for access to its ecosystem, including navigation and SLAM packages. A unique feature is its user-friendly robot control, allowing researchers to define the robot as a Unity NavMesh Agent with built-in path planning and navigation. This abstraction simplifies interaction with the robot, much like a non-player character (NPC) in a video game, especially when its capabilities align with those of a virtual agent, ensuring smoother control.

At its current state, the FEROX Simulator currently supports three types of robots, each providing distinct ROS services. This includes small Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for forestry exploration and mapping, along with large UAVs and Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs) for berry transportation. These diverse platforms are designed for various wild berry collection scenarios, enabling researchers to optimize robot behaviors in challenging real-world conditions, ultimately enhancing human-robot collaboration.

2.5 Humans

The FEROX Simulator stands out by enabling users to control avatars similar to video game characters. Each human instance operates on a separate machine, creating a third-person human picker multiplayer simulator. This feature distinguishes it from other simulators that focus mainly on the robotic perspective and plays a crucial role in HRC development.

Users can perform actions like requesting specific robotic services, such as tasking a UAV for mapping designated regions or arranging rendezvous with it. They can also interact with the environment by collecting berries from bushes and loading them onto the robots. These activities closely resemble real-world tasks, allowing researchers to test and refine HRC strategies. Furthermore, The simulator further engages users through gamification. A scoring system awards points based on the number of berries they collect, creating a "coopetitive" environment where users can collaborate or compete in berry picking. This not only adds enjoyment but also explores various collaborative and competitive dynamics in HRC scenarios.

3 Conclusion

The FEROX Simulator stands as a tool for modern HRC in advanced industrial applications. It addresses the need for realistic simulators in modern robotic domains, where AI-driven robots can significantly augment human capabilities. This simulator, purpose-built for robot-assisted wild berry collection, offers a comprehensive platform to explore and optimise multi-human multi-robot collaboration. Future work involves expanding the simulator’s capabilities and facilitating seamless content sharing between human and robot instances, further solidifying its position as a valuable asset in advancing HRC research and development. A stable version of the FEROX simulator is expected to be made freely available in Q1 2024.

References

1. Ajoudani, A., Zanchettin, A.M., Ivaldi, S., Albu-Schäffer, A., Kosuge, K., Khatib, O.: Progress and prospects of the human–robot collaboration. *Autonomous Robots* **42**, 957–975 (2018)
2. Carpin, S., Lewis, M., Wang, J., Balakirsky, S., Scrapper, C.: Usarsim: a robot simulator for research and education. In: *Proceedings 2007 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. pp. 1400–1405. IEEE (2007)
3. Echeverria, G., Lassabe, N., Degroote, A., Lemaignan, S.: Modular open robots simulation engine: Morse. In: *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. pp. 46–51. IEEE (2011)
4. Koenig, N., Howard, A.: Design and use paradigms for gazebo, an open-source multi-robot simulator. In: *2004 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)(IEEE Cat. No. 04CH37566)*. vol. 3, pp. 2149–2154. IEEE (2004)
5. Kudelski, M., Gambardella, L.M., Di Caro, G.A.: Robonetsim: An integrated framework for multi-robot and network simulation. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **61**(5), 483–496 (2013)
6. Mizuchi, Y., Inamura, T.: Cloud-based multimodal human-robot interaction simulator utilizing ros and unity frameworks. In: *2017 IEEE/SICE International Symposium on System Integration (SII)*. pp. 948–955. IEEE (2017)
7. Pinciroli, C., Trianni, V., O’Grady, R., Pini, G., Brutschy, A., Brambilla, M., Mathews, N., Ferrante, E., Di Caro, G., Ducatelle, F., et al.: Argos: a modular, multi-engine simulator for heterogeneous swarm robotics. In: *2011 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. pp. 5027–5034. IEEE (2011)
8. Quigley, M., Conley, K., Gerkey, B., Faust, J., Foote, T., Leibs, J., Wheeler, R., Ng, A.Y., et al.: Ros: an open-source robot operating system. In: *ICRA workshop on open source software*. vol. 3, p. 5. Kobe, Japan (2009)
9. Rohmer, E., Singh, S.P., Freese, M.: V-rep: A versatile and scalable robot simulation framework. In: *2013 IEEE/RSJ international conference on intelligent robots and systems*. pp. 1321–1326. IEEE (2013)
10. Yalçinkaya, B., Couceiro, M.S., Soares, S.P., Valente, A.: Human-aware collaborative robots in the wild: Coping with uncertainty in activity recognition. *Sensors* **23**(7), 3388 (2023)